

Abstract

This research investigates the application of deep learning models, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), for Fusarium Head Blight (FHB) detection in wheat crops with RGB images. The study explores the challenges of field-based detection, proposes methodologies for building a diverse dataset, training a deep learning model on it and discusses the obtained results. The document aims to contribute to the development of efficient tools for FHB detection in real-world field conditions.

Fusarium Head Blight detection in wheat with deep learning and RGB images

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) stands as one of the world's most important cereal crops that plays a crucial role in global food security, nourishing billions of people across the globe [1]. Its cultivation dates back to ancient civilizations, with evidence of wheat domestication in the Fertile Crescent around 10,000 years ago [2]. Today, wheat is a staple food in many regions, providing essential nutrients such as carbohydrates, protein, fiber, and vitamins [3].

However it is vulnerable to various threats, and among them, Fusarium Head Blight (FHB), also known as scab or tombstone, stands out as a menacing fungal disease to the global wheat production [4]. FHB, caused by the fungus *Fusarium graminearum* [5], not only causes yield losses but also introduces mycotoxins [6], posing risks to both agricultural economies, human health and livestock. The *Fusarium* species, thriving in cool and humid conditions during wheat flowering stages, have a global impact on wheat cultivation. FHB manifests in various symptoms, including partial or complete bleaching of spikelets, the tiny flower clusters that produce wheat grains. Infected grains become discolored, shriveled, and lightweight, significantly reducing overall yield [7].

Traditional detection methods relied on laborious processes, such as visually inspecting wheat heads for signs of infection, bleaching, discoloration, and the presence of spore masses [8] or the transportation of wheat samples to controlled laboratory settings for chemical analysis of mycotoxins [9]. Despite offering valuable insights, these methods proved resource-intensive, time-consuming, and limited in applicability to dynamic field conditions or large-scale agricultural operations.

The evolution of deep learning models, presents a promising shift in Fusarium Head Blight detection paradigms. Departing from the constraints of laboratory-centric approaches, researchers are exploring the potential of these models in real-world field experiments [10], despite the environmental challenges it poses, the diverse and dynamic lighting conditions, changing optical properties of the soil due to wetting and drying, and diverse spatial patterns which result in highly complex and constantly changing scenes [11].

The emergence of deep learning, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), has revolutionized the field of agriculture, offering a promising solution

for FHB detection. Deep learning models, trained on vast datasets of images of wheat heads, can automatically identify and classify infected and healthy florets with good accuracy [12]. These models can significantly accelerate the FHB detection process compared to traditional methods. Automated image analysis can be performed in real-time [13], allowing farmers to make timely decisions about fungicide applications and crop management strategies. This timely intervention can help to minimize yield losses and protect the health of consumers and livestock. They are also relatively inexpensive to develop and deploy, making them a cost-effective solution for FHB management [14].

This research project aims to delve into the integration of deep learning models for Fusarium Head Blight detection in wheat crops. By addressing the limitations of traditional detection methods, the study seeks to contribute to the development of accurate, efficient, and practical tools for FHB detection. In doing so, providing a solution that can enhance disease detection strategies in the field, leveraging the power of computer vision techniques.

1.2 Objectives

1.2.1 Investigate The Topic

Enhancing Knowledge on Wheat Plants and FHB

The first objective i had involved a comprehensive exploration of relevant research papers to deepen understanding of wheat plants and the Fusarium disease. The focus is on unraveling the intricacies of wheat biology, disease manifestation, and preventive measures employed in agricultural practices such as crop rotation [15][16][17][18].

Surveying Deep Learning Models for Fusarium Detection

The second objective is to survey current advancements in deep learning models specifically those that were used in recent studies and showed promising results. This entails a thorough analysis of existing literature, evaluating the performances of various deep learning models, and identifying those with promising results in similar tasks [19] [20].

Selection and Adaptation of Deep Learning Models

Building on the findings from the literature survey, a subset of pretrained deep learning models will be selected based on their demonstrated efficacy in wheat or Fusarium classification, detection or related tasks. The chosen models will undergo a critical examination of their methodologies, strengths, and limitations. These selected models will serve as the foundation for the subsequent model training phase, as discussed in detail in its section.

1.2.2 Acquire and Curate Field Datasets

Build a diverse and representative datasets from field experiments, ensuring variability in lighting conditions, environmental factors, and stages of wheat growth. Implement a meticulous data annotation step. Curate the annotated

dataset by applying preprocessing and data augmentation techniques to facilitate the training step of the model.

1.2.3 Explore Transfer Learning Techniques

Explore the applicability of transfer learning techniques to leverage pre-trained models for related plant diseases or imaging tasks. Investigate how transfer learning can enhance the efficiency of FHB detection models, especially in situations with limited labeled data.

1.2.4 Assess Model Results

Evaluate the results obtained and test the generalizability of the developed deep learning models across different wheat varieties. Investigate the adaptability of these models to varying environmental and agronomic conditions to ensure broader applicability.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Timely detection is crucial for effective disease management and since FHB epidemics have increased in the last decades due to changes in agricultural practices and expanded wheat cultivation. Weather conditions, particularly warm and rainy days during anthesis, contribute to FHB incidence. Europe has sporadic FHB occurrences, with yield losses reaching 40-50% in some regions. China, Canada, and the USA have faced severe FHB outbreaks, causing significant economic losses. Latin America reported seventeen FHB epidemics in Argentina, with losses of up to 70%. Brazil observed an increased FHB-risk index since the 1960s. Limited information is available for FHB in Australia, but a severe outbreak occurred in 2010 [21].

Traditional approaches involved transferring wheat samples to a laboratory for sample analysis or optical detection which is a resource-intensive process. This literature review explores the application of deep learning models in field experiments for Fusarium head blight detection on wheat, examining both its strengths and weaknesses while also aiming to scrutinize the methodologies employed across these applications.

2.1.1 Challenges in Field-Based Detection

The transition from controlled environments to field conditions poses challenges, Deep learning models, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which have shown remarkable capabilities in image analysis and pattern recognition, offer promise when used in a controlled settings but face limitations when applied directly to field experiments. These challenges, such as variable lighting conditions, background clutter, strong wind, rain and outdoor complexities stand in the way of achieving good results for these models. this section underscore the need for research addressing the unique aspects of field-based experiments on FHB detection.

2.2 Review of Studies

In this section, we will explore the applications of deep learning in research papers, examining the advantages it has brought, the outcomes obtained, any identified limitations, and exploring potential similarities with the current research.

2.2.1 Current State of Research

The application of deep learning for Fusarium detection has been explored in controlled environment agriculture (CEA), laboratories, and open fields. Results from CEA and laboratory settings have generally shown high accuracy. For instance, in the research conducted by Hamila et al [22], a 3D multispectral scanner was employed in a lab, providing a stable approach for observing Fusarium in kernels, facilitating labeling, and a smoother CNN training step, achieving a 100% accuracy on RGB images during testing. Other studies by Leirdal et al [23] focusing on wheat grains for a detailed analysis of FHB anomalies also obtained high results, with an average accuracy of 98%.

However, challenges arise in open field experiments due to environmental factors, resulting in lower accuracies. In the study by Rößle et al [24], FHB classification by severity using a pretrained image classification model, EfficientNet (B0), with RGB cameras, yielded an average accuracy of 48.3% in training and 40.5% in testing. Another research project, similar to the current one, focused on object detection in open field conditions. Su et al [25] trained a Mask R-CNN pretrained model, achieving an average precision of 63.68% for FHB detection and 65.14% for FHB instance segmentation.

These experiments highlight a significant drop in precision when transitioning to outdoor conditions, emphasizing the challenges faced in real-world environments.

limitations

despite the several advantages of the usage of deep learning in these researches, it also faces limitations that could hinder the work progress.

the high computational intensity: deep learning models, especially object detection ones, requires significant computational resources which can pose a problem to researches done with limited resources as in this model used by Su et al [25] when forced to use a batch size of 4 due to the lack of GPU memory.

Data dependancy: Deep learning models heavily rely on large and diverse datasets for training. In the context of FHB detection, obtaining extensive labeled datasets can be challenging, particularly in open field conditions with complex environmental variables.

Also labeling datasets for model training, can be time-consuming and subjective. Annotating images for FHB detection requires domain knowledge and expertise, contributing to the overall complexity of deploying deep learning solutions.

Model's generalization: Deep learning models are susceptible to overfitting, Overfit models may perform well on training data but struggle with generalization to new, unseen data.

2.2.2 Research Gaps and Future Directions

However, a noticeable gap persists in the literature concerning object detection models developed for the purpose of FHB detection in the open field.

It is noteworthy to emphasize that a substantial portion of prior research primarily focused on the classification of FHB rather than its direct detection. Some studies were dedicated to categorizing the severity of FHB, while others concentrated solely on classifying its presence. In contrast, the primary objective of the current research is to achieve the accurate and direct detection of the diseased spikelets within the wheat plant. This distinction underscores contribution of this study in addressing the specific challenge of detecting FHB on site, within the natural and dynamic environment of wheat fields.

There is as well a notable gap in these projects concerning the diversity of their datasets and that the data was collected in closed environments not representing real world conditions. While controlled environment agriculture (CEA) or lab experiments show promising results, their application in real-world environments may prove ineffective due to the opposite nature of environment that these models were trained on and the need to transport the samples to a lab in order scan it and run inference on it makes it in a way similar to the traditional method of chemical analysis of mycotoxin which proved to be costly and time consuming. In the case of datasets built in open fields, the images are often too zoomed in, featuring a limited number of kernels (ranging from 5 to 12 at most) and taken in a way to reduce background noise as much as possible [25]. while they might yield decent results but, again, Such datasets are impractical for real-world scenarios or for achieving faster detection in large-scale agricultural operations.

therefore, the focus of future research should be directed towards developing deep learning applications that enable efficient (FHB) detection in real-life settings, ultimately enhancing the speed and reliability of agricultural operations while minimizing yield loss.

This section emphasizes the need to address all these challenges mentioned above, explore innovative approaches, and develop diverse datasets representative of various field environments. Closing these gaps will enhance the understanding of FHB dynamics and contribute to reducing the time needed for detection and implementation of effective FHB management strategies.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

3.1.1 Study Area

The images utilized in this research were captured in an experimental open air farm located in As, Norway. The study area encompassed two distinct farms dedicated to the cultivation of winter wheat and spring wheat, respectively. Both fields were enclosed with sprinklers, for Mist irrigation in order to control humidity creating a conducive environment to promote the spread of FHB.

The use of imagery from both farms aimed to provide a comprehensive dataset that covers the variations in wheat crops relevant to FHB in different seasonal contexts.

3.1.2 initial approach

In our initial approach, we aimed to acquire aerial data using a "DJI Mavic 3" Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) our primary objective during the flights was to achieve an optimal balance between altitude and image resolution. We sought to ascend to the highest feasible altitude while ensuring that the resultant images maintained sufficient clarity to facilitate precise annotation of spikelets. This careful consideration aimed to provide a detailed and comprehensive visual record of the wheat crops, specifically focusing on the developmental aspects relevant to fusarium. This aerial survey encompassed the two distinct types of wheat fields, the winter wheat and spring wheat.

A second objective was to diversify the dataset. Flights were conducted to capture images from diverse angles, altitudes, and perspectives,

The flights were designed to encompass varying angles and altitudes, The starting altitude was set at 5 meters, gradually decreased to 1 meter over different flights. This altitude variation aimed to simulate real-world conditions where aerial surveillance may involve flying at different heights.

The UAV captured images at three different angles — 90 degrees, 60 degrees, and 30 degrees — in both forward and backward orientations. Sideways images were also obtained, ensuring a comprehensive dataset that encapsulated the crop development from various viewpoints.

limitations

While utilizing UAV images for disease monitoring offers valuable insights, certain limitations were encountered during the data collection process. These limitations include:

Image Resolution at Higher Altitudes: At elevated altitudes, the image resolution diminished, as shown in figures 3.1 and 3.2, impacting the clarity required for precise disease identification. The reduced sharpness at higher altitudes posed challenges in discerning intricate details of the crops and accurately detecting instances of fusarium.

Figure 3.1: UAV image from a 5m altitude

Figure 3.2: Zoomed in UAV image

Crop Disturbance at Lower Altitudes: Operating the UAV at lower altitudes, presented a challenge due to the disturbance caused by the propellers. The close proximity of the UAV to the crops led to the generation of turbulent air, resulting in crop movement and blurring in the captured images. This phenomenon made it arduous to obtain sharply defined images necessary for meticulous annotation and analysis.

3.1.3 Secondary approach

a custom-built Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) (figure 3.3) for agricultural purposes created by the Norwegian university of life sciences(NMBU) robotics team served as a pivotal tool. In this setup, the Mavic UAV was placed on the UGV and securely fixated to serve as an RGB camera for data collection. The intentional slow movements of the UGV contributed to enhanced stability, resulting in the acquisition of clearer and more precise images. The images used to build the dataset were captured with a 45 degree angle from an altitude of 2 meters in sunny conditions and clear sky.

limitations

However, this approach presented certain limitations. The operation of the robot was not a solo task; it necessitated the coordination of three individuals.

Figure 3.3: Robot used to capture the images.

One person was responsible for controlling the robot, another for clearing obstacles and directing the robot from an alternate vantage point, and a third for capturing the images. The narrow field lanes posed a challenge, restricting the robot’s freedom of movement within them without risking damage to the crops.

Furthermore, the robot’s movement was constrained to a sideways unidirectional path, forward and backward paths were not possible due to the UGV bigger width. This restricted mobility, combined with fixed altitudes and angles used for image capture, resulted in a less diverse dataset. The inability to vary these parameters limited the range of perspectives captured during the data collection process.

3.2 Data preprocessing and annotation

After acquiring the images, a first step of filtering was manually done to clear duplicates and images containing only the soil in between plots. After the first filtering process, they were divided into four quadrants, resulting in four separate images. Each of these quadrant images was further subdivided into four parts, yielding a total of sixteen smaller images derived from a single original image. This subdivision aimed to enhance the focus on individual spikelets and clarify the presence of diseases. the original image dimensions were 5280x3956, after dividing it the final image dimensions were 1320x989 which were later resized before the training phase according to the maximum size the pretrained model would take.

Following the subdivision, a second filtering process was applied to select images with the clear quality for wheat heads. Some images exhibited condensed and unclear wheat crops around the edges, making it challenging to annotate diseases with certainty. To ensure the dataset's integrity and precision, images were carefully filtered to retain those displaying optimal clarity and visibility of spikelets. Once the dataset was refined through this filtering process, the annotation phase commenced.

Figure 3.4: Image Division

For the annotation of the dataset, the *COCO Annotator* tool was employed, creating two classes: "wheatheads" and "diseasedPart". The inclusion of "wheatheads" in the detection aimed to guide the model in associating Fusarium Head Blight (FHB) specifically within the wheat heads, reducing the likelihood of confusion with other plants or parts of the soil that might share similar colors in the images.

Figure 3.5: Annotated image.

A total of 300 images were annotated, containing the following number of instances for each class as shown in table 3.1

Class	Instances
wheatheads	25,706
diseasedPart	10,866

Table 3.1: Number of Instances for Each Class

The process took around 2 months, for each image annotation process it took approximately 30 40 minutes per image on average. The limited number of annotated images in the dataset is attributed to the time-intensive nature of the task. After annotating the images, an auto-orientation process was applied. This step ensures consistent alignment and orientation of the images for further processing.

3.3 Data Augmentation

Following annotation, data augmentation techniques were applied to enhance the dataset. Augmentation helps increase the diversity of the training set, improving the model's generalization capabilities. The following augmentation techniques were employed:

- **Flip:** Horizontal, Vertical
- **Rotate:** 90° Clockwise, 90° Counter-Clockwise
- **Crop:** 0% Minimum Zoom, 20% Maximum Zoom

These augmentation strategies aims to have a bigger, more diverse, training set, allowing the model to learn robust features and patterns during the training process. The augmentation process increased the size of the dataset to a total of 700 images, providing a richer set of examples for the model to learn from. strategies that involved changing level of contrast or saturation

were avoided based on a study[24] that stated that it decreased the learning potential of FHB, citing back the reason that This could be attributed to the significance of both color and brightness in accurately detecting wheat heads. Introducing augmentation in the color spectrum might alter these key indicators, potentially causing variations in the detection of FHB. Manipulating the color spectrum may either diminish or intensify the differentiation between color regions excessively, leading to unclear detection outcomes.

Finally, the dataset was split into a 70% 30% split for train and validation, while the test dataset was taken from unused, unannotated data, also data from other datasets [32] as well where used to test the model generalizability.

3.4 Model Training

The chosen approach for model training embraced the methodology of transfer learning, a technique known for its ability to leverage pre-existing knowledge and enhance the efficiency of learning on a new task. Several models were chosen for training based on previous performances in research papers related to disease or plant detection with Yolov5 showing great promise in object detection [19], the pretrained models were Faster R-CNN, Mask R-CNN[26], YOLOv5 [27], and YOLOv8 [28] a version even better than Yolov5. Among these, YOLOv8 results emerged as the most promising, showcasing better performance, hence, only yolov8 results will be discussed.

YOLOv8, a CNN-based model, was released in January 2023 by Ultralytics. They provided five scaled versions: YOLOv8n (nano), YOLOv8s (small), YOLOv8m (medium), YOLOv8l (large) and YOLOv8x (extra-large). YOLOv8 supports multiple vision tasks such as object detection, segmentation, pose estimation, tracking, and classification.

for this task, due to limited computational resources, Yolov8s in object detection mode was chosen, yolov8s in segmentation mode was also tested but had lower accuracy.

Yolov8 architecture

The YOLOv8 architecture utilizes a modified CSPDarknet53 backbone, introducing the C2f module as a replacement for YOLOv5’s CSPLayer. This module, denoting cross-stage partial bottleneck with two convolutions, merges high-level features and contextual information, enhancing detection accuracy. A spatial pyramid pooling fast (SPPF) layer accelerates computation by pooling features into a fixed-size map, and each convolution is accompanied by batch normalization and SiLU activation.

YOLOv8 adopts an anchor-free model with a decoupled head, independently managing objectness, classification, and regression tasks. This design allows each branch to concentrate on its designated task, contributing to overall model accuracy. In the output layer, YOLOv8 utilizes the sigmoid function for objectness score activation, representing the probability of an object within the bounding box. Class probabilities, indicating the likelihood of objects belonging to specific classes, are computed using the softmax function.

To address bounding-box loss, YOLOv8 incorporates the CIoU [30] and DFL [31] loss functions, while binary cross-entropy is employed for classification loss.

These loss functions have demonstrated efficacy in improving object detection performance, particularly for smaller objects.

Figure 3.6: YOLOv8 architecture, image from [28].

3.4.1 Model evaluation

To assess the model's performance, various metrics were considered:

- **Precision:** The ratio of true positive predictions to the sum of true positives and false positives:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

Precision indicates the accuracy of positive predictions made by the model. A higher precision means fewer false positives, demonstrating the model's ability to avoid mistakenly labeling non-FHB instances as positive.

- **Recall:** The ratio of true positive predictions to the sum of true positives and false negatives:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

Recall measures the model’s ability to correctly identify all relevant instances of FHB. A higher recall indicates that the model captures a larger proportion of true positive instances, minimizing false negatives.

- **F1 Score:** The harmonic mean of precision and recall, given by the formula:

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

F1 score balances the trade-off between precision and recall. It is particularly useful in this case since there is an uneven class distribution or when both false positives and false negatives are critical. A higher F1 score indicates a model that performs well in terms of both precision and recall.

- **Mean average precision (mAP@50)**

- It evaluates the precision of a model across different confidence thresholds, considering the overlap (Intersection over Union or IoU) between predicted bounding boxes and ground truth bounding boxes. The IoU threshold is set at 50%, meaning that a predicted bounding box is considered correct if it has at least 50% overlap with a ground truth bounding box.

The mAP@50 is calculated by averaging the precision values at different confidence thresholds. Precision is calculated at each threshold, and then the average precision (AP) is computed. The mAP is the mean of these average precision values.

mAP@50 provides insights into the model’s precision across various confidence levels, offering a more nuanced evaluation than a single precision value. It considers how well the model performs at different levels of confidence in its predictions.

Let $P(\text{IoU})$ represent precision at a specific IoU threshold. The mAP@50 is calculated as the mean average precision over multiple IoU thresholds, typically ranging from 0.5 to 0.95. given by the formula:

$$\text{mAP@50} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n P(\text{IoU}_i)$$

The precise calculation involves integrating the precision-recall curve for each class and then averaging over all classes.

These metrics collectively provide a comprehensive evaluation of the model’s ability to accurately detect Fusarium Head Blight in wheat crops and if it shows promise to generalize on new data.

3.4.2 Training phase

Various experiments were conducted to optimize the model’s performance, utilizing both Google Colab and a local environment. The Colab setup featured a robust configuration with 12GB RAM, a Tesla T4 GPU equipped with 15GB GDDR6 memory, and 2,560 CUDA cores. In comparison, the local setup included 8GB DDR5 RAM, an Nvidia GTX 1060 GPU with 6GB memory and

high-quality settings, along with an Intel Core i5 7300HQ processor boasting 4 cores.

To accommodate the model’s capabilities, all images were resized to a maximum dimension of 640. The exploration of parameters during these trials led to the identification of optimal settings that yielded the best results.

A total of 100 epochs was set due to computational resources, but it allowed the model to undergo sufficient training iterations(77 per epoch) without risking overfitting. A small batch size of 8 is chosen, increasing the number of iterations per epoch and enhancing the model’s ability to generalize and learn from data samples in each iteration. Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) is employed as the optimizer, a widely-used and versatile choice for training deep neural networks due to its natural regularizing effect which can help prevent overfitting, especially in our case when the amount of training data is limited. Adam and AdamW optimizers were also tested before opting for SGD , The optimal learning rate of 0.01 is a balanced setting, ensuring steady progress in updating the model weights without oscillating or converging too slowly which was tested in previous trials. Additionally, the inclusion of weight decay at 0.001 helps prevent overfitting as well by penalizing large weights during training. Overall, these parameter choices demonstrate a thoughtful balance between training efficiency and model generalization

Parameter	Value
Number of Epochs	100
Batch Size	8
Optimizer	Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)
Learning Rate	0.01
Weight decay	0.001

Table 3.2: Training Configuration

To address concerns about potential bias towards the wheatheads caused by the imbalanced class distribution in the initial model which could cause a lower mAP for the "diseasedPart" class, a second experiment was conducted. In this experiment, the "wheathead" class was excluded from the dataset, focusing solely on the "diseasedPart" class. The parameters of the first model were retained, with the only modification being a reduction in the number of training epochs to 60. This adjustment aimed to prevent overtraining due to the limited number of instances.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 First Model

4.1.1 Train metrics

For the initial model,

During the training step, the gradual decrease in losses indicates promising progress during training for both classes, by taking a closer look into the evaluation metrics we'll find that the "wheathead" class shows more promising progress with high mAP, scoring in the end a value of 90,3% figure(4.1), on the other hand we notice that the "diseasedPart" despite also its losses reducing gradually and its mAP improving gradually with each epoch, but the amount that it's increasing with is low, scoring a value of 58.% (figure 4.2), With decreasing losses and improving validation metrics. Convergence is suggested around epochs 80-90, where consistent performance metrics are observed.

the mAP for the whole model scored 74.1%, which is the average between the 2 classes

Figure 4.1: Train loss.

A refined explanation of the loss values for better understanding of these graphs: **Box_Loss (Bounding Box Regression Loss):** The box loss quantifies the disparity between the predicted bounding box coordinates and the actual ground truth. Lower values indicate a higher precision in the model's prediction of object bounding box coordinates, reflecting improved localization accuracy.

Cls_Loss (Classification Loss): The cls loss evaluates the accuracy of the predicted class probabilities in comparison to the true class labels. Reduced values signify more precise predictions of the object's class by the model.

DFL_Loss (Deformable Convolution Layer Loss): The dfl loss gauges the error in deformable convolution layers, specifically designed to enhance the model's proficiency in detecting objects with diverse scales and aspect ratios. Decreasing values indicate improved model performance in handling object deformation and variations in appearance.

Figure 4.2: Precision Recall curve.

For the confusion matrix, it provides a detailed breakdown of the model's performance by showing the number of true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative predictions for each class in the dataset. As for the F1 score, an average of 69% was achieved, indicating the model's ability to correctly identify instances of each class while minimizing both false positives and false negatives.

Figure 4.3: F1 confidence curve.

The F1-confidence curve provides a balance between precision and recall across different confidence thresholds. The peak F1 score at 70% is significant, indicating an optimal trade-off at a confidence threshold of 32,2%.

Figure 4.4: Confusion Matrix.

In Figure 4.4, the model’s performance on classifying instances is presented. Notably, around 48% of instances truly belonging to the "diseasedPart" class are correctly predicted, while approximately 2% are misclassified as "Wheathead" and about 51% as "Background." Regarding the "Wheathead" class, the model achieves an 88% correct prediction rate, with 12% misclassified as "Background." In contrast, the "Background" class experiences misclassifications, with approximately 32% predicted as "diseasedPart" and 68% as "Wheathead" by the model.

4.1.2 Validation metrics

Similar results were obtained from the validation step, with performance metrics closely mirroring those achieved during the training phase, albeit with a slight reduction in values. These results will be systematically compared and thoroughly interpreted in the subsequent section to gain insights into the model’s generalization capabilities and its ability to perform well on new, unseen data. The comparison will shed light on any potential overfitting or underfitting tendencies, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the model’s robustness and effectiveness across both training and validation datasets.

Figure 4.5: Validation loss.

Figure 4.6: Precision Recall

Figure 4.7: F1 confidence

Figure 4.8: Confusion Matrix.

4.2 Second Model

4.2.1 Train metrics

For the second model, detecting only the "diseasedPart".

The loss values are steadily decreasing per epochs indicating good training progress, we notice from the graphs that there isn't much improvement from the previous model, the losses reducing gradually in low rates and the mAP increasing gradually in low rate as well, scoring for mAP 59.2% which is 1.2% higher than with the "wheathead" class included.

for the confusion matrix, the results were exactly the same in training while slightly less, 0.2%, in validation.

Figure 4.9: Train loss.

Figure 4.10: Precision Recall

Figure 4.11: F1 confidence

Figure 4.12: Confusion Matrix.

4.2.2 Validation metrics

While mAP for the single class model in training was slightly higher than the multi-class model, in validation the mAP is slightly less, 0.5%, than with the "wheathead" class included. The same goes for the confusion matrix as well with 0.02% less for correctly detected "diseasedPart"

Figure 4.13: Validation loss.

Figure 4.14: Precision Recall

Figure 4.15: F1 confidence

Figure 4.16: Confusion Matrix.

4.2.3 Conclusion

The concerns that were raised by having an imbalanced instances were addressed, the results obtained from excluding the "wheathead" class didn't have a significant effect on the mAP of the model indicating that there's no bias towards detecting it while neglecting FHB detection.

4.3 Predicted Images

In this section, we present inferred samples from the test dataset, along with additional samples from another dataset used to assess the model's generalizability. The showcased examples aim to provide insights into the model's performance on unseen data and its ability to generalize beyond the training set. By including samples from a different dataset, we evaluate the model's adaptability to diverse scenarios and assess its robustness in handling variations in input data. This approach enhances the comprehensive understanding of the model's capabilities and extends insights into its potential application across broader datasets and real-world conditions.

Test images from original dataset

Figure 4.17: Samples from the Predicted images compared with its originals.

Test images from external dataset [32]

It's promising to observe that the model can generalize well to unseen data, While there may be instances that the model missed, but overall it was able to detect a good amount of the instances wether FHB or wheat head.

(a) External dataset

(b) Predicted

(c) External dataset

(d) Predicted

Figure 4.18: Samples from the Predicted images from an external dataset compared with its originals.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of results

for the The training and validation loss values (figure 4.1) & (figure 4.5), starting with the box loss values which demonstrate a consistent pattern of convergence, with both training and validation losses steadily decreasing over the course of epochs. The training box loss reached its minimum value of approximately 0.94036 at epoch 99, the last one, indicating effective bounding box regression during training. On the other hand, the validation box loss, which represents the model's performance on unseen data, also exhibited a decreasing trend. The validation loss values are generally higher than the corresponding training loss, as expected due to the unseen nature of validation data. This alignment between the training and validation losses suggests that the model generalized well to unseen data, showing similar improvements in bounding box regression performance on both datasets.

the cls loss values reveals a similar trend to the box loss. Both the training and validation cls loss consistently decrease across epochs, indicating that the model effectively improves its ability to classify objects. The training cls loss reaches its minimum value of approximately 0.54802 at epoch 99, the last epoch, indicating that the model achieved a high level of accuracy in predicting class probabilities during the training phase. The validation cls loss values are generally higher than their corresponding training values, reflecting the model's performance on unseen data. This alignment in decreasing loss values suggests that the model generalizes well to new instances, demonstrating consistent improvements in classification performance on both training and validation datasets.

The loss values reaching their minimum at the last epoch indicates that it is still decreasing and that there still might be room for improvement if trained more, but it wasn't feasible due to computational resources.

The comparison between the training and validation results reveals consistent and reliable performance of the deep learning model across both phases. Notably, the F1-confidence curve indicates a balanced performance in terms of precision and recall, with the model achieving an F1 score of 70% at a confidence threshold of 32.2% during training and 70% at 32.%1 during validation. The precision-confidence curve highlights the model's high precision, maintaining a

perfect precision of 100% at a confidence threshold of 91.6% in both phases. Additionally, the precision-recall curve values for "diseasedPart" 58%, "wheat-head" 90.3%, and an overall mAP of 74.1% during training closely match the corresponding values of 57.7%, 90.3%, and 74% during validation, demonstrating consistent class-specific performance. The recall-confidence curve, reaching 87% at a confidence threshold of 0.00 in both training and validation, signifies the model's ability to capture a higher proportion of true positives at lower confidence thresholds. Overall, these findings indicate the model's robust generalization to new, unseen data, reinforcing its reliability and effectiveness across different datasets.

The provided confusion matrices for both the training and validation steps show similar patterns in the model's classification performance across different classes. In both cases, the model demonstrates strong accuracy in predicting instances from the "Wheathead" class, with approximately 88% accuracy. Additionally, the "diseasedPart" class is predicted with similar accuracy, around 48%. The confusion matrix for the "Background" class also indicates a consistent accuracy of approximately 68%.

the results of the confusion matrix and the low values of mAP recorded for FHB detection takes us back to the limitations of not having enough FHB instances as well as the environmental challenges and the noticed genral confusion of the model with background and the predicted classes shows how the backgrounds could influence the precision of a model.

In summary, the deep learning model demonstrated effective performance in bounding box regression and object classification, showing consistent improvements across training and validation phases. The convergence of loss values and alignment between training and validation results indicate robust generalization to unseen data. but would still face limitations due to relatively low mAP value for FHB and limited dataset it was exposed to. Although the model reached minimum loss at the last epoch, resource limitations prevented further training.

Precision and recall curves displayed a balanced F1 score and high precision, with class-specific performance. Confusion matrices highlighted accurate predictions for "Wheathead" and "diseasedPart" classes, but challenges in FHB detection were observed due to limited instances and environmental factors which affected the model's correct predictions.

Acknowledging these limitations, it's clear that background noises impact precision, influencing mAP values. Despite challenges, the study provides insights into the model's reliability and effectiveness, suggesting areas for improvement in dataset diversity and addressing environmental complexities in future research.

5.2 Comparison with Literature

The literature review highlights a significant gap in research concerning field-based object detection models for FHB detection on wheat crops. It emphasizes that the majority of studies tend to concentrate on closed-set models [33], neglecting the crucial aspect of open field experiments. This gap underscores the need for more comprehensive investigations and developments in the field of FHB detection, particularly in real-world agricultural settings.

The outcomes of this research project echo the challenges delineated in the

earlier review of studies, particularly those encountered in open field experiments [25]. These challenges span from the initial stages of image acquisition and the endeavor to secure favorable weather conditions to the deliberate effort to capture images under various circumstances, thereby enriching the dataset for real-world applicability. Moving through the data annotation phase, a critical and time-consuming step, which takes months to accomplish, necessitating expertise in disease detection, perfection in annotating diseased parts becomes paramount. Any inaccuracies in this phase could potentially render the entire model ineffective. Finally, the precision of deep learning models experiences a discernible decline in uncontrolled environments, primarily attributed to background distractions. This drop becomes evident when the models grapple with the task of detecting or classifying small, complex, and irregular fusarium shapes.

5.3 Future Research

Utilize UAVs with Advanced Cameras

Invest in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with high-resolution cameras to capture clear details of wheat heads from elevated positions. Despite potential high costs, this enhancement is crucial for improving the dataset's applicability in real-world scenarios.

Explore UGVs for Field Detection

If UAVs are not feasible, consider employing Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGVs) equipped with cameras for field detection. To implement this, strategically plant wheat fields to accommodate UGV dimensions, allowing for free movement. Additionally, incorporate an altitude adjustment mechanism for the camera to modify its height as needed.

Augment Fusarium Instances

Increase the number of instances of Fusarium in the dataset to enhance precision. Expose the model to a more extensive range of instances across various conditions and growth stages. This diversification ensures that the model becomes adept at detecting Fusarium in diverse scenarios, contributing to overall accuracy and precision.

5.4 Conclusion

Despite facing challenges in image acquisition and dataset construction, the outcomes of the study show great promise. The implemented model demonstrated significant potential and achieved commendable results.

The limitations encountered during the image acquisition and dataset construction phases underscore the complexities inherent in real-world scenarios. However, the positive performance of the model suggests that with further refinement and enhancement of the dataset, the deep learning approach can be a valuable tool for FHB detection in open field experiments.

The project lays the groundwork for future developments in agricultural image analysis. The promising results encourage continued research and improvements in data collection methods to enhance the model's robustness. The insights gained contribute to the ongoing efforts to combat FHB, emphasizing the potential of deep learning in revolutionizing disease detection in agricultural settings.

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